

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

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“WHEN WEDDING BELLS RANG TRUE”

In Grade One's hushed, gentle beginning,
A friend sat with open heart.
He had the smile I remember still,
A boy who hardly spoke at all.
I was a visitor, only face—
Then gone from that school without a trace.

The years rushed on, as time does do,
Our lives grew far apart, old and new.
Sixteen long years had passed and gone,
When fate, unrevealed, took him along.
One day he stood at my gate,
A love reborn, a twist of fate.

He went through the town, he made inquiry,
Until finally, my name was discovered.
I heard him speak, my heart brimmed,
And in my heart, the wedding bells.
They say you know when love is right—
That moment reflected a holy light.

We both had stories of love once aglow,
That dimmed little by little to the night.
Eight years we each had tried and wept,
In quietness, dreams and hope had passed on.
But out of the ashes, pure and white,
A love came back, both sure and strong.

He'd been abroad for eight hard years,
Through foreign lands and secret tears.
But something pulled him back once more,
To follow the past through joy and sorrow.

And there I stood, still waiting there,
Unaware that love was in the air.

We met once more, this time as two
Who knew the price of false love.
We exchanged our hurts, we exchanged our dreams,
And sewed our hearts with tender stitches.
In months, not years, we exchanged "I do,"
And constructed a life that kept growing.

Now two little souls claim us as their own,
Their giggles make our home a home.
And in his eyes, I still see
The boy who sat beside me.
It seems like we've always been
Together, in life's thick and thin.

So here we are, through joy and strife,
Forever tied as man and wife.
From schoolboy days to adult grace,
I envision my future in his face.
The past had misdirected us both—
But true love found its way somehow.

